

Pairing Disparate Datasets for Generative Outputs Across Music and Architecture

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Abstract. Most multimodal models utilise semantically consistent data samples for model training and generative outputs. However, for design and composition work, semantic correlations are not the only means for cross-modal translations as suggested by synaesthetic phenomena. In this paper, we propose several methods to pair disparate datasets for training a model to translate between musical compositions and architectural design. We adopt and augment our own datasets to extract high-level features for both music and architectural samples. We utilise self-organising maps and agglomerative clustering strategies to pair data which is then used to train a conditional GAN. The techniques are evaluated through qualitative and quantitative assessment and are also applied in generating architectural compositions. Our experiments suggest promising initial results for feature pairing using hierarchical agglomerative clustering when generating images. We conclude by discussing the meaning and utilization of our proposed techniques as a means to systematically design with abstract features across modalities.

Keywords: cross-modal translation · multimodal design · data pairing · generative adversarial networks · computational design.

1 Introduction

Research regarding multimodal models has undergone major development over recent years and has dramatically expanded generative capabilities for translation between domains. Models adopting diffusion decoder based techniques have excelled at translations between text and image formats [15, 9, 8, 4] while more recent LLM based foundation models are now extended to function bi-directionally across domains including text, audio, video and images [11, 6]. Most of these developments are focused on performing semantic based translations and require large-scale, well-annotated and aligned datasets. In these cases relationships between modalities are pre-determined by natural multivalence established through

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association in common context or a single state. An example of this, in the context of space and sound, is the development of polychoral music in response to the opposing chorister positions in St Mark’s Basilica, which suggests a linkage between auditory and spatial modalities conditioned by a single source [22].

While most studies depend on the mentioned pre-existing semantic relationships to simulate already established links between modalities, few discuss the opportunities of developing synthetic relationships across disparate and yet familiar domains. Historically, architects have adopted such multidisciplinary approaches towards reference material from other fields and modalities to develop new designs. Eisenamans 1987 competition entry for the Biozentrum [21] and Xenakis’ design for the 1958 Philips Pavilion [20] are examples of how genetic code and music were cross-referenced to develop spatial outputs. However, these proposals are dependent on direct translations without broader pattern recognition capabilities.

Instead of limiting generative outputs to a preexisting semantic context or adopting rule-based translations, this study explores strategies of applying data pairing techniques to train models on disparate datasets. We propose that by pairing naturally unpaired data, it is possible to establish synthetic connections for working with abstractions systematically. By encoding and decoding information, the role of references is extended to include abstract and complex patterns that are inaccessible to people through traditional means of computation or comprehension. The strategies covered in this paper build on the historic use of cross-disciplinary references in the field of architectural design. Therefore, although our proposed techniques are applicable to a broad range of data types, the study is focused on pairing independent data across music and architectural domains.

It is important to note that the research was conducted during 2021-2022, when state-of-the-art model architectures, such as visual transformers or diffusion networks, were in their infancy. The proposed methodologies were appropriate for the time, but may not reflect the current state-of-the-art techniques and high-fidelity results. Regardless, we believe that the work still holds value for the proposed data pairing strategies, the case study and discussion on future improvements.

2 Method

State-of-the-art multi-modal models such as CLIP [3] and AudioCLIP [2] rely on pre-existing paired data where images or audio are paired with descriptive labels to perform cross-modal translations. For these models, natural language facilitates consistency between the embedding spaces for each data point.

However, consistently paired information is often not available when considering alternative and somewhat unlikely cross-modal relationships such as audio and 3D space. Besides acoustic properties, these modalities are not often comparable and lack a semantically meaningful or readily interpretable com-

mon description. Without this, they can not be trained to create a common embedding without prior processing and pairing.

To synthesise connections between architecture and music, we propose a pipeline linking unrelated data between architectural models and audio. This data is used to train a CNN model on 12 musical styles and a series of building shapes derived from 6 classical portland stone structures in London.

2.1 Data Representation, Collection and Augmentation

For both datasets, we chose to encode spatial and auditory expression into an RGB image format with a $3 \times 256 \times 256$ shaped array. Although our initial ambition was to train the encoder network using 3D architectural information, in our experiments this has proven challenging due to the lack of available curated 3D datasets and issues with non-homologous samples for working with convolutional neural networks. Open source datasets for 2D [5] or 3D CAD information [18, 19], are limited in architectural qualities. Popular repositories such as ShapeNet [19] focus on the shapes of everyday objects rather than large-scale spaces or buildings, which limit training models for traditional architectural output. Furthermore, as 3D models do not necessarily translate to consistent homologous tensors, they have to be pre-processed using point clouds or voxelisation techniques. In our experience, these tend to create outputs with substantially more visual noise.

We also propose to pre-process audio information and convert it into the same image format. Although 1D mono audio samples are more manageable, the RGB format allows us to keep each data sample homologous for training and pairing purposes. This is also helpful for evaluation as the generated output can be visually compared.

The architectural image dataset consists of 3 subsets for plans, sections and elevations. This is proposed in mind of traditional architectural drawing types used to embed 3D information into 2D space, which can also be used for re-creating 3D models. To develop the dataset, first, 3D CAD models of 6 Portland Stone buildings in London are subdivided into individual rooms. Then a series of plans, sections and elevation depth maps are extracted from each model. To capture the variety of spatial qualities, sections are cut at regular intervals across each model. This allows to augment the dataset as multiple sections, plans and elevations can be extracted from a single model. The output geometry is then rescaled for consistent inputs and converted into images.

For the audio dataset, over 27 hours of music is chosen by the author from 12 genres to ensure variety and diversity between the samples. We used the Librosa library to convert each audio sample into mel spectrograms, which were then processed to match the dimensionality of the building dataset for training consistency. After conversion, each sample was split into multiple $3 \times 256 \times 256$ images to provide homologous samples which roughly correlate to 5 second increments.

As seen in Fig. 1 and table 1 the smaller dataset of architectural drawings is not as dense or evenly spread out as the spectrogram dataset. In our early

Fig. 1: Architectural section dataset distribution using t-SNE

tests, we found the models trained on the initial architectural dataset underperformed when compared to the versions trained on augmented datasets. We therefore trained three StyleGAN2-ADA [14] models for 1,840 steps and used the generated outputs to augment each of the architectural datasets. Although no new original samples are provided in the augmented dataset, we believe the improvements are driven by the adjustments to the embedding positions regarding density and vector distance between samples. Improvements through aligning dataset sample embeddings are further covered in the discussion sections.

Table 1: Dataset sample sizes for original and augmented datasets.

Dataset	Original	Augmented
Architectural plan dataset samples	284	20,000
Architectural section dataset samples	646	20,000
Architectural elevation dataset samples	1,296	20,000
Mel spectrogram dataset samples	19,069	-

2.2 Feature Extraction and Pairing

As each sample consists of 196,608 dimensions, we first encode them into higher level embeddings to improve the computational efficiency of the pairing process. To meaningfully reduce the dimensionality of the images, each sample is run through a modified large scale VGG-16 model [17]. The final two layers of the model are frozen and replaced with a fully connected feedforward layer outputting 4,000 dimensional embeddings. The large scale pre-trained VGG model

reduces the dimensionality of the inputs with considered compromise to the original samples by utilizing the abstraction from the initial convolutional layers. Due to the broad training set of the original VGG model, we believe the produced embeddings retain most of the initial features. The dimensionality of the generated outputs is further reduced to two dimensions using t-distributed Stochastic Neighbour Embedding (t-SNE) [16].

We propose two approaches for pairing the disparate datasets. First by using Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering with Ward's method to pair data based on feature clusters, and secondly by using Self-Organising-Maps (SOM) [13] to pair on a sample basis [1].

Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering (HAC) To automatically cluster the 2D embeddings, Ward's method for Hierarchical Agglomerative clustering from the Scikit library is used to partition data into clusters. The 2D t-SNE embeddings allow to make clear distinctions between clusters with differing features (see Fig. 2). These are then paired recursively following greedy matching based on shortest distance. This logic is then applied again for the samples within each paired cluster. Any leftover samples without pairs are pruned.

Fig. 2: Architectural section and spectrogram dataset t-SNE representations partitioned using Ward's method for agglomerative clustering with 9 and 50 clusters

Self-Organising-Map Overlay (SOM) Each of the datasets is reorganised using Self-Organising-Maps. We used the Somoclu library to reshape each of the 2D embedding sets into matching arrays of the same shape. This allowed us to restructure float information into a more controlled spatial arrangement while preserving the initial relative relationships between the samples. This can be seen through the U-matrix maps of each SOM (see Fig. 3) After a series of tests we derived that a 65 by 65 array produced an optimal density grid. Each sample was then paired based on correlating coordinates of each matrix with any duplicates culled. As with agglomerative clustering, we ended up with 3 paired datasets to test.

Fig. 3: Section and Mel spectrogram representations through SOMs. The u-matrices on the left highlight the differences between the two distributions.

2.3 Model Architecture

To perform the cross-modal translation, a Pix2Pix style CNN model [12] is trained on the paired datasets. The model architecture is chosen for its simplicity and ease of training and is implemented using PyTorch and trained on a single RTX-4070-12GB GPU. Samples were separated into training and validation sets using a 90/10 ratio for each dataset. After a series of tests we opted to use a batch size of 32 with 100,000 steps for the architectural models and 70,000 steps for the spectrogram models. Once trained, the supervised models can generate outputs from one sample to another. However, the model architecture does not permit bidirectional translations, meaning that two sets of models have to be trained for bidirectional translation between samples.

Table 2: Dataset sample sizes for original and augmented datasets.

Methodology	Dataset	Training pairs	Test pairs
HAC-Ward-50	Augmented	13,702	1,523
HAC-Ward-9	Augmented	13,436	1,493
HAC-Ward-50	Original	536	60
SOM	Augmented	2,621	25
Random	Augmented	16,667	1,852

3 Results

3.1 Evaluation Methodology

To quantitatively evaluate model performance, we tested generated outputs with LPIPS [10], CMMD and KID evaluation metrics. The LPIPS metric was used to assess output accuracy and was derived through the average score of 500 generated samples compared to ground truth images. In addition, the CMMD [23] and KID [24] metrics were used to assess how well on average the statistical distribution matched between 500 generated outputs and 1000 reference images to review sample diversity and semantic content. All the input, reference and ground truth images were sampled outside the training or test datasets. However, as these techniques rely on pre-trained classifiers using data that is largely dissimilar to our implemented datasets, the results can be inaccurate.

We therefore additionally conducted an anonymous survey for a subjective qualitative assessment.¹ 20 participants were asked to evaluate visual image clarity (V-clarity), image continuity (V-continuity) and audio clarity (A-clarity) for each pairing methodology. We provided a set of 15 randomly sampled outputs for the visual clarity assessment, 10 generated outputs for the image continuity assessment and 5 sets of 5 second audio for the audio clarity assessment. The image continuity samples were generated using a latent walk sequence of mel spectrogram samples extracted using StyleGAN2-ADA. For audio and visual clarity, all sample sets were generated using identical input data. For the audio samples, the Griffin-Lim Algorithm (GLA) [7] was used to rebuild the spectrograms into audio. The participants were also provided with reference material for 'very good' and 'very poor' samples and asked to evaluate each methodology on an integer scale from 0-10. For a consistent evaluation across quantitative and qualitative metrics, the survey results were inverted by subtracting each score from 10 such that lower scores indicated better performance. We used the Friedman test to conduct whether participants rated the five methodologies differently. For this, mean ranks were calculated for each methodology, with lower ranks indicating better perceived performance. Statistical significance was evaluated at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Both the quantitative and qualitative evaluation metrics were applied to the HAC and SOM pairing techniques using the architectural (A) and spectrogram (S) outputs. To test cluster count and data augmentation strategies, we also included separate results for HAC using the augmented dataset with 9 and 50 clusters and the original (OG) dataset with 50 clusters. As a comparative test, we also introduced a random (RND) pairing. Samples for each methodology are available in the appendix.

¹ Survey evaluation samples are available from the following link:
<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/11OXbehUfLQCoPC9xn0-K2pzRSwPQw-RP?usp=sharing>

Table 3: Methodology performance across quantitative and qualitative metrics (lower is better). The qualitative measurements (V-clarity, V-continuity and A-clarity) are represented as the mean ranks of each methodology.

Methodology	LPIPS	CMMD	KID	V-clarity	V-continuity	A-clarity
HAC-50-A	0.1894	0.0205	0.1428	1.500	2.175	-
HAC-9-A	0.2119	0.0376	0.2622	2.400	2.200	-
HAC-50-A-OG	0.4591	0.3906	2.7497	4.900	4.300	-
SOM-A	0.4264	0.2432	1.7143	4.075	3.225	-
RND-A	0.5492	0.2095	1.4225	2.125	3.100	-
HAC-50-S	0.2541	0.1338	0.8956	-	-	2.275
HAC-9-S	0.2490	0.1494	1.0033	-	-	3.275
SOM-S	0.2310	0.2144	1.4166	-	-	2.000
RND-S	0.4388	0.1885	1.2484	-	-	2.450

Fig. 4: Methodology performance across quantitative and qualitative metrics (lower is better).

3.2 Result Evaluation

For the qualitative assessment when generating section outputs, HAC with 50 clusters achieved the best performance in all three LPIPS (0.1894), CMMD

(0.0205) and KID (0.1428) metrics. The second-best score in all three categories was also HAC with 9 clusters, which suggests that a difference in cluster count has impact on both accuracy and distribution. While SOM-A scored third regarding LPIPS, it performed worse than the HAC-50-A-OG and RND-A regarding the CMMD (0.2432) and KID (1.7143) distribution metrics.

For spectrogram pairing, SOM scored best for accuracy with the lowest LPIPS (0.2310). However, the difference is marginal as HAC-50-S and HAC-9-S both produced comparable results. Notably, both HAC variants outperformed SOM-S regarding CMMD and KID distribution metrics, suggesting a better overall distribution alignment despite lower accuracy.

For the qualitative visual clarity assessment, the Friedman test revealed significant differences in participant ratings across all five methodologies ($\chi^2 = 66.46$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$). Participants consistently rated HAC-50-A highest (1.50), while HAC-50-A-OG received the lowest ratings (4.90). The original dataset score was also worse than random pairing, suggesting that data augmentation to align dataset distribution substantially improves visual output quality. For visual continuity the Friedman test revealed a similar pattern with significant differences across the methodologies ($\chi^2 = 25.46$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$) with HAC-50-A scoring best (2.175). Finally, for audio clarity the Friedman test also showcased significant differences between methodologies ($\chi^2 = 11.72$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.05$). In contrary to the visual assessments, SOM-S scored the best (2.000) and HAC-9-S received the lowest rating (3.275). The differences between the mean rank of each methodology here are the least significant between the 3 assessments. We attribute the reduced significance between methodologies to artifacts introduced by the Griffin-Lim Algorithm (GLA) for spectrogram to audio translation. The GLA often results in low reconstruction quality due to the cost function only accounting for consistency rather than characteristics of the target signal. Alternative methodologies for encoding and decoding audio information should be considered in future research.

4 Discussion

4.1 Model Evaluation

The results show that our proposed data-pairing techniques lead to improvements for generated image and audio quality when compared to a random pairing. This showcases the validity of the discussed data pairing strategies even with modestly sized datasets.

Of the proposed techniques, HAC-50 achieved superior performance in almost all evaluation metrics across both section and spectrogram datasets. We believe the superior performance stems from the ability to identify higher-level features common across samples within each cluster, enabling more robust cross-modal translations. As such, the number of unique or similar samples within a cluster directly influences the granularity of features that are translated across modalities. However, this suggests that abstract pairings using fewer and larger

clusters can also discount nuanced features and lead to poorer performance. This can be noticed in the performance differential between HAC-50-A and HAC-9-A. We believe the 9 cluster model likely had groups containing disparate samples, which resulted in lower-quality outputs, as the model struggled to identify stable features amid high cluster sample variance.

We believe SOM addresses the pairing abstraction concerns inherent to HAC, as pairings are made on a sample-by-sample basis across the entire dataset. However, the relatively poorer SOM performance is likely due to asymmetries in how the two datasets map onto the embedding space. Direct sample-to-sample correspondence requires symmetrical embeddings with aligned coordinates, which is unlikely given the different distributions between the architectural and audio feature spaces.

We believe future research should focus on distribution alignment techniques that extract and pair samples across the full embedding space while taking account for the similarity of each sample. A possible approach involves masking or down-weighting regions of the embedding space where samples exhibit low correspondence or have distant embedding coordinates, effectively focusing the pairing process on areas of strong cross-modal alignment. Such techniques could improve pairing quality by ensuring that fewer samples with greater distances between embedding coordinates get paired.

4.2 Dataset Limitations

The results suggest there are inherent limits to the translation capabilities based on the used data types. Both the spectrogram and the architectural models were trained using the same pairings, however the spectrogram model showcases generally poorer quantitative results than the models for section image output. We believe this is due to data resolution, as architectural images are not as granular as the densely encoded mel spectrograms. It is possible that due to the simplicity of the section drawings and complexity of the spectrograms, nuanced control over more subtle features such as vibrato or expressiveness are limited. A more coarse representation of audio information such as the MIDI format could be more aligned in terms of feature complexity per sample. Subject to testing, this might further improve model performance as well as provide an alternative to reconstructing higher fidelity audio recordings.

4.3 Case Study: Application for 3D Model Generation

To explore the creative potential of our model, we applied it to generate 50 architectural forms from musical inputs outside the training dataset. Each of the samples were used to generate a set of section, elevation and plan drawings. These were then vectorised and processed using Grasshopper for Rhino into 3D architectural models.²

² Further videos on the case study are available at <https://youtu.be/QhKh1w2pkdg> and <https://youtu.be/aGfHUV2KZk8>

The generated geometry is significantly different from the original models used in the dataset, however, key features can still be differentiated, such as the dome and pilaster structures of St Paul's Cathedral. Differences can be attributed to the model capabilities, as most of the generated outputs are of lower quality than the original dataset. Further differences can also be attributed to the parametric modelling process, where 2D data is used to construct 3D shapes. It should be noted that although the neural network and parametric modelling process distorts the information, it is applied consistently across all samples.

From a creative standpoint, output interpretation becomes a subjective task. As seen in Fig. 5 there is no clear visual correlation between the spectrogram and the final architectural element. Although the results seem relatively clean, all pre-existing semantic meaning between the two pairs is lost. As the datasets are disparate, the translations are also not necessarily interpretable. Prior assumptions on musical style correlation with architectural forms are no longer valid, as meaning between the translations now depends on the internal parameters of the model.

Correlations can however be implied by manipulating feature pairings which are isolated during the clustering process. This opens space for creative supervision, as designers are encouraged to curate the pairing process for interpretability. With this in mind, the techniques rely on designer authorship in shaping meaning across modalities.

The proposed pairing approach is not bound by the suggested modalities and can be generalised to any dataset by embedding information in lower dimensions. This flexibility offers integrating multimodal considerations within architectural workflows. When applied correctly, these techniques suggest a mode of formalised synaesthesia, where the dialectical interplay of data in multiple modalities generates unique meaning.

Fig. 5: Generated architectural shapes from audio samples. Note the displayed spectrograms are inverted.

5 Conclusion

The paper discussed a series of approaches for pairing disparate datasets through high level embeddings and training generative models for cross-modal translations. From the methods discussed, we concluded that HAC using Ward's method is the most successful technique tested. We also provided recommendations for improvements to the training and pairing process. We believe future research adopting these techniques should focus on improving augmentation strategies to match the distribution of the datasets for more accurate pairing.

There are substantial improvements to be made, however, these processes provide opportunities to manipulate unrelated information at scales and abstractions previously unavailable to designers. The opportunity to point to hidden patterns within datasets unavoidably changes the role of references. We believe these techniques can be eventually applied to any type of data, allowing architects and composers to cross-reference between features of different modalities without relying on formalised taxonomy or resemblance of high-level symbolic representations.

Appendix

Generated section images using HAC-50-A

Generated section images using HAC-50-A

Generated section images using HAC-9-A

Generated section images using HAC-50-A-OG

Generated section images using SOM-A

Generated section images using RND-A

Fig. 6: Generated section images using a latent walk of a StyleGAN-ADA model trained on mel spectrograms. The samples were used for visual continuity evaluation

Fig. 7: Generated section drawings using mel spectrogram inputs. The samples are a sub-set of the visual clarity evaluation.

Fig. 8: Generated mel spectrograms using section drawing inputs. The samples were used to generate audio for the audio clarity evaluation.

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